

Assessing the Organizational Communication Style and its Effect on Employees' Performance in the Case of Wachemo University

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ABSTRACT

In the case of Wachemo University, this paper looks into evaluating organizational communication style and how it affects employee performance. 261 sample respondents were given a standardized questionnaire as part of the study's survey methodology. The study's aims were achieved by combining the dependent variable, employee performance in the organization, with the independent variables completeness, correctness, consideration, clarity, conciseness, courtesy, and concreteness. Vice Presidents of Academic Affairs, Research and Community Service, and Administrative and Development are all involved in this investigation. The sample was chosen purposefully within each office: from the academic vice-president office, the colleges of business and economics, social science, and agricultural science were chosen; from the research and community service vice-president office, the following institutions were chosen: Community service directorate office, Research publication office, and Research directorate office. The finance office and Student service office were chosen from the administrative and development vice-president office. Following collection, the data was analyzed using tables and graphs that use descriptive statistics. Additionally, a multiple linear regression model was employed to investigate how changes in each of the study's independent factors affected how well the employees performed. The results demonstrate that every independent variable has a favorable and significant impact on how well an organization's employees perform. Affective commitment and the communication surrounding work and organization were both favorably impacted by social and emotional subjects that were discussed between superiors and subordinates. The organization should build a fluid communication style between different departments in order for them to better coordinate and cooperate in order to achieve the overall organizational goals, according to the results and recommendations

INTRODUCTION

The human resource poses the biggest difficulty among the production variables since, in contrast to other inputs, employee management necessitates expert handling of thoughts, sentiments, and emotions in order to ensure maximum efficiency. In this challenge, organizational communication is crucial. It is possible to generate and enable low productivity with a high degree of worker boredom and disarray if leaders or managers of any organization are unable to coordinate a perfect and seamless flow of communication interaction among employees and the outside business environment. People, however, comprehend and interpret messages in various ways. The correctness of a message being transmitted can be interfered with by a variety of undesired interferences in communication, which poses a threat to effective communication (Koontz, 2001).

Wang (2005) It has frequently been theorized from the standpoint of human resource management that an employee's knowledge, aptitude, and skill set will enable them to be a good performer upon hiring. Therefore, management must design its goals and rules so that workers carry out their jobs and complete their given responsibilities. Communication systems are fast changing at this time, and they are constantly being asked to play a bigger part in the effort to achieve economic and political stability. They are crucial for the success and growth of an organization.

The cornerstone to an organization's success is effective workplace performance, and how effective the workers are will decide how successful the organization is. In order for employees to know what is expected of them and for managers to ensure that each employee has immediate access to the resources they need to complete each assignment given to them, there must be effective communication between the two parties. Every action the management takes to improve employee performance falls under the category of communication.

Statement of the Problem

According to Hellweg & Phillips (2012), worker productivity increases when there is communication within the organization. Besides many other things communication within the organization helps the employees to perform their tasks well, to have information about the duties they have to perform, and about the goals of the organization. They argue that existence of communication within the organization lead to the effective decision-making.

A study by University of East London shows that the concept of communication is immeasurable in modern management, and it seeks to meet clear understanding between manager and all the employees. It explains that employee communication is; infect exchange and clear provision of information, commands and directions between management and employees. And it makes the organization to work properly and employees to be well aware about their responsibilities and duties. (University of East London, 2009).

Specifically, the study was trying to answer the following research questions

1. What is the structure of communication that exists at Wachemo University?
2. What is the relationship between effective organizational communication and employee performance?

3. How does communication improve employee performance?
4. Which one is the most useful channel of communication from an employee's point of view?
5. What are the barriers and failures to organizational communication systems?

Hypothesis

After careful concern of all independent variables and the dependent variable of the study, the following hypotheses were developed.

Ho1 : The performance of the employee and completeness are not significantly correlated.

Ho2 : There is no connection between employee performance and correctness that is noteworthy.

Ho3 : The performance of the employee and consideration have no real connection.

Ho4 : Performance of the employee and Clarity do not significantly correlate.

Ho5 : Performance of the employee and conciseness do not significantly correlate.

Ho6 : There is no connection between courtesy and an employee's output.

Ho7 : Performance of the employee and Concreteness do not significantly correlate.

Objectives of the Study

1. General Objective

The general objective of this research is to assess the organizational communication style and its effect on employee's performance.

2. Specific Objective

To assess the communication structure of Wachemo University

To determine how employee performance is impacted by communication

To examine the connection between productive organizational communication and workers' output.

To determine the most effective means of communication from the perspective of the workforce.

To determine the organizational communication system's obstacles and shortcomings.

3. Significance of the Study

➤ People exchange their thoughts, feelings, ideas, and emotions through communication. By getting to know one another and sharing the same love for life, man fulfills his wants while also helping others. Humans are social creatures. He is unable to handle worldly affairs on his own. To perform his routine actions, he requires assistance from others. It is possible to send messages from one person to another through communication. The findings of this research will benefit Wachemo University by:

- Higher quality of services and products
- Greater levels of trust and commitment
- Increased employee engagement and higher levels of creativity
- Greater employee job satisfaction and morale of employees
- Better workplace relationships
- Greater acceptance of change
- Reduced staff turnover

- Less organizational unrest
- Reduced costs
- Helps an employee understand the terms and conditions of their employment and drives their commitment and loyalty.
- The Wachemo University personnel will receive useful information from the research regarding the effectiveness, dependability, and economy of their communications policies, practices, and programs. The study will give Wachemo University staff members knowledge about the impact of effective communication and how ineffective communication has negatively impacted employee performance. The study will then recommend strategies for improving communication to boost employee performance.

4. Scope of the Study

The study restricts its scope to Wachemo University and defines it in line with the factors specified in the hypothesis due to time, resource, and other constraints. Furthermore, it was finished inside a year.

5. Limitations of the Study

It was quite challenging for the researcher to do the study completely free of any issues or constraints. As with all studies, this one has its limitations. Some respondents failed to return the questionnaires by the deadline, which caused a delay in the researcher's ability to submit the report by the deadline. Other respondents failed to return the questionnaires entirely. In addition, some respondents had demanding jobs, and others weren't as eager to complete the questionnaires. Therefore, these and other such issues could have had an impact on the paper's quality, which could have limited the outcome.

6. Organization of the Study

There are five chapters in this work. Introduction, Statement of the Problem, Research Questions, and Objective of the Study with General Objective and Specific Objectives are all included in Chapter 1 along with the study's Significance, Scope, and Organization. The second chapter reviews relevant literature. Empirical and theoretical reviews are also undertaken there, organizing the literature review and creating a conceptual framework. The third chapter examines research methodology, data collection methods, sampling methods, sample sizes, data processing methods, model testing, and operationalization of variables, instrument validity and reliability, as well as ethical issues. The results of the data analysis and interpretation are reported in chapter four. The findings are compiled in chapter five, along with the conclusions and recommendations.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Review of Related Literature

Theoretical Basis of Organizational Communication

The idea of effective communication on employee performance and its research have been founded on a number of theories, the most popular of which are probably the systems theory, classical, and human relations theories. These theories explain how an organization behaves, communicates, and, more especially, how well it communicates. The idea essentially provides methods from which the researcher can employ effective communication to gauge internal

performance within an organization in this setting. Given this, the Human Relations Approach and Systems Approach will receive a lot of attention because they provide a comprehensive view of an organization. According to the system theory, an organization is a system of interconnected, related pieces.

Defining Communication

According to Keyton (2011), communication is the process of conveying knowledge and a shared understanding from one person to another. The Latin word *communis*, which meaning "common," is the source of the English term "communication." The term emphasizes the reality that there can be no communication until there is an understanding that arises from the sharing of knowledge. According to Cheney (2011), Figure 1 illustrates the concept and lists the critical components of the communication process. By comparing the definitions provided by many authors, a more precise definition of communication can be found. These definitions include some of the following: Communication takes place when two parties exchange messages that have a common meaning. "The process of exchanging ideas or information between humans is known as communication. Communication is the process of conveying messages (facts, ideas, attitudes, & opinions) from one person to another so that they are understood. "People exchanging their thoughts, ideas, and feelings with one another in terms that are easily understood is known as communication.

You might have noticed that all of the definitions listed above have something in common. All of the definitions emphasize that communication requires at least two participants and some sort of message that is meant to be passed from one side to another. In addition, when people communicate, they do so in a form that is understandable to one another. They exchange information among themselves.

Figure 1. The Communication Process

The sender and the receiver are two components that are present in every communication exchange. By deciding whatever words, symbols, or gestures to use to create a message, the sender encodes the notion. The result of the encoding, which can be expressed through spoken, nonverbal, or written language, is the message. The communication is decoded by the receiver into useful information. Finally, feedback happens when the recipient reacts to the sender's message and sends it back. The sender can get feedback to see if their communication was received and understood. A school administrator or other organization representative can pick from a variety of written media, including memos, letters, reports, bulletin boards, handbooks, newsletters, and the like. When information supports one's own opinions, people are more likely to accept it, Feedback Medium Receiver Encode Encode Sender Encode Noise Message Decode Needs

and Values (Keyton, 2010). The ability of the school administrator to collaborate with other school stakeholders (faculty, support staff, community members, parents, central office) and develop a shared understanding of what the school/school district is trying to achieve, where it wants to go, and a shared sense of commitments that people have to make in order to advance the school/school district towards a shared vision and clarity of goals is crucial for success in the modern school. The effectiveness of the school or school district will increase when administrators are able to create a shared purpose, vision, values, and goals.

Organizational Communication

The sender conveys a message to the recipient through communication, either verbally or nonverbally. One of the main obstacles to successful organizational performance is ineffective communication (Robbins et al. To achieve both organizational and individual goals, communication, for instance, enables members of the organization to discuss pertinent organizational issues, produce and share information for developing ideas, and reach decisions. Members communicate orders, update one another on changes, and work together to solve issues and make improvements.

Types of Communication in Organization

In line with Greenberg and Baron's assertion (2008, 355). There are two categories for communication: (1) Internal and (2) External, depending on whether it takes place inside or outside the organization. Two categories are taken into consideration depending on the type of communication, such as (1) Formal and (2) Informal. Three types of communication have been identified from the perspective of the flow of communication. They are (1) lateral, (2) upward, and (3) downhill. Three categories of communication have been identified, depending on the medium or form: (1) Written (2) Oral or Spoken (both together constitute Verbal), and (3) Non-Verbal. Each of these is covered in detail in the section that follows.

Internal and External Communication

- Internal Communication

Within an organization, information is transmitted through internal communication. There are several ways to communicate with businesses, including memos, reports, meetings, face-to-face conversations, teleconferences, video conferences, notices, etc. An essential tool for handling business-related issues is internal communication.

- External Communication

Communication with individuals outside of an organization is known as external communication. Business letters, press releases, advertisements, leaflets, invitations, telegrams, proposals, and more are examples of external communication. External messages can have a significant impact on an organization's reputation and eventual success.

Formal and Informal Communication

Formal Communication

The channels of power within the organization are followed in formal communication. The organization has purposefully created formal channels of communication. Thus, formal communication refers to the chain of command

that establishes the flow and course of official messages between persons or organizational divisions. Thus, formal communication refers to the chain of command that establishes the flow and course of official messages between persons or organizational divisions. Formal communication typically moves in four different directions; Diagonal, horizontal, upward, downward, and up.

- Downward Communication

A manager and a subordinate may be involved, or it may span several levels of the organization. Downward communication refers to official messages sent from managers and supervisors to subordinates.

- Upward Communication

Without upward communication, management would be oblivious to how their downward signals were received and perceived by the workforce, missing out on key insights and denying employees the opportunity to join the organization. Management needs to understand what is going on in the organization in order to solve issues and make wise decisions.

- Horizontal Communication

Information flow between people working at the same organizational level, such as departments, is known as horizontal communication. For the following reasons, horizontal communication is crucial in an organization

- Diagonal Communication

Teams made up of people from different functional areas and even different hierarchical levels are used in some organizational models.

Informal Communication

Organizations have informal channels of communication in addition to formal channels. Informal communication develops as a result of social ties that develop within an organization and cannot or should not be done through official channels. Informal avenues of communication exist due to both their distinct advantages and the flaws in formal channels of communication. However, communicating through formal channels is a time-consuming process that results in long delays between the time a message is sent and when a response is received. As a result, formal channels are ineffective for managing crises, meeting unexpected communication needs, effectively communicating complex or detailed information, and sharing information. The grapevine typically carries personal interest items if an organization's administrators are honest with their staff and send all relevant information through proper channels. However, when the official lines of communication fall short, rumors about the company start to circulate through the grapevine. In other words, "the grapevine only becomes involved in official problems when the formal channels of transmission fail to communicate, are misunderstood, or are rejected by the intended audience.

Verbal and Non-Verbal Communication

Verbal Communication

Verbal communication is the written or spoken exchange of ideas through words. It can occur at different levels (individually, in a group, or over the phone), through a variety of channels, and at different times. A manager's duties include a substantial amount of verbal communication. For instance, the majority of managers conduct phone calls, speak in person, and deliver presentations.

According to research, managers spend up to 90% of their overall communication time talking to each other.

- **Written Communication**

The message is created in black and white, as the name would imply. Business letters, memoranda, reports, resumes, written telephone messages, newsletters, policy manuals, etc. are all examples of written communications. It is a fairly popular method of communication in most businesses and is appropriate in a variety of circumstances.

- **Oral Communication**

In this form of communication, the two parties share ideas or messages by speaking out to one another. Through spoken words, the message—instruction order, command, etc.—is communicated. Numerous modes of communication, including conferences, committee meetings, interviews, phone conversations, face-to-face meetings, etc., use this technique.

Nonverbal Communication

Information that is communicated through actions and behaviours as opposed to spoken or written words is referred to as nonverbal communication. Because it affects the messages communicated and received, it is essential to shared understanding and meaning. In actuality, nonverbal cues including voice inflections, hand gestures, facial emotions, and even attire worn contribute significantly to common understanding. The emotional state of the sender is also communicated by nonverbal cues, and this is frequently the most crucial aspect of the message. There is a lot of subconscious or unconscious nonverbal communication. Consider that you are trying to hear the lecture in your business communication class. Although it can be used independently, nonverbal communication typically complements verbal communication. Nonverbal cues make up the majority of the message we convey in addition to our words. As the discussion goes on, you might start replacing your words with gestures, such as nodding your head and smiling to indicate approval or frowning to indicate reservations.

Principles of Effective Communication

The seven (7) indicators listed below were used by Ainobushoborozi (2013) to achieve effective communication.

Completeness – According to communication theorists, communication must always be comprehensive while delivering all information the intended audience needs to know. Information is encoded with concern for the decoder's ideas and then transmitted. According to research done by Ainobushoborozi (2013), the following are some characteristics of complete communication: communication completeness helps build and enhance an organization's reputation.

Conciseness Ainobushoborozi (2013) stressed that, it is the act of delivering an intended message in least possible words without foregoing the other essentials of information. Communication in such ways is both timesaving as well as cost saving. It accentuates and emphasizes the main message as it avoids using unwarranted and needless words. According to the researcher, essential messages are only presented to the audience.

Consideration – It entails taking into account others' concerns. The audience, including their perspectives, backgrounds, mindsets, educational levels, etc.,

must be taken into account for communication to be effective. Make an effort to anticipate your audience's needs, feelings, and issues. Make sure the audience's dignity is upheld and their emotions are not harmed. Change the message's wording while keeping it complete to meet the audience's needs. The following are characteristics of mindful communication: Focusing on "you" personalizes issues, helps you connect with your audience, shows that you care about them, and encourages a positive response from them. Focus on using phrases like happy, committed, thank you, warm, healthy, and help.

Clarity - Clarity indicates focusing on one message or goal at a time rather than attempting to do too much at once. Communication that is clear facilitates understanding. According to Ainobushoborozi (2013), precise, relevant, and concrete word choice strengthens the meaning of a message when thoughts and concepts are completely clear.

Concreteness - Concrete in communication implies being particular and clear rather than fuzzy and general. Concreteness strengthens confidence. Features in concrete messages are that it is supported with specific facts and figures. Words used are clear and build a reputation. Concrete messages are not misinterpreted.

Courtesy Nothing is more crucial than conveying a message in a polite and moral manner. This action aids the sender in establishing some amount of credibility with the recipient. It suggests that the recipient is inclined to accept the message that is being sold. A message should be courteous if it respects the recipient and conveys the sender's feelings.

Correctness - The absence of grammatical errors in communication is a sign that it is correct. The accuracy, correctness, and timing of the message are indicators of effective communication. Correct statements increase self-assurance and have a bigger impact on the audience or readers. Additionally, it ensures that the facts and numbers utilized in the message are precise and accurate and uses language that is suitable and correct.

Barriers to Effective Communication

Nothing is more important for a school administrator to do than to improve communication (Pauley, 2010). Then why does communication fail? The solution appears to be quite straightforward. The sender, the encoding, the message, the medium, the decoding, the receiver, and the feedback are the aspects of communication that I have identified. Complete understanding and clarity are not achieved if there is any noise in these components. The biggest issue with communication, according to the author George Bernard Shaw, is the false sense of accomplishment that results from it (Shaw, 2011). Process barriers, physical obstacles, semantic barriers, and psychosocial barriers are the four categories of impediments (referred to as "noise," see Figure 1) (Eisenberg, 2010). Effective and good communication depends on each stage of the communication process. Steps that become stuck create barriers. Think about the following scenarios:

Sender restriction At a meeting led by the superintendent, a new administrator with an original concept stays silent out of concern for criticism.

- Encoding impediment An administrator who speaks English is unable to understand a staff member's complaint regarding working conditions.

moderate barrier Instead of expressing her concerns in person, a really upset staff member writes the boss a highly charged letter.

- Disambiguation difficulty An elder principal is unsure of what a youthful department head means when he describes a teacher as "spaced out."
- Receiver barrier: Because the school administrator was not paying close attention to the dialogue because she was engaged with creating the annual budget, she asked a staff member to repeat a comment.
- A lack of inquiries from school officials during a meeting creates a feedback barrier that makes the superintendent question whether any meaningful comprehension has occurred. As a complicated give-and-take process, communication can break down at any point in the cycle, which can prevent the transfer of understanding.

i. Physical Barriers The effectiveness of communication can be hampered by a variety of physical distractions, such as a phone call, unexpected visits, and physical distances between persons, barriers, and radio static. Physical barriers can occasionally be removed, but people frequently take them for granted. For instance, a wall that is awkwardly placed can be taken down. It is possible to stop interruptions like phone calls and walk-in guests by giving a secretary instructions. People can be separated by distance thanks to the right media.

ii. Semantic Barriers There are various communication hurdles that are brought on by the words we use, how we use them, and the meanings we give them. Semantics, or the meaning of the words we employ, is the issue. Distinct people may have distinct meanings for the same word. Efficiency, greater productivity, managerial discretion, and just cause are just a few examples of words and phrases that may mean one thing to a school administrator and something quite another to a staff member. Communication difficulties caused by semantics are also influenced by technology. The intricate school systems of today are quite specialized. Staff and technological specialists in schools create and use specialized language that only other staff and technical experts of a like caliber can comprehend. People cannot understand the message if they cannot understand the language.

iii. Psychosocial Barriers Fields of experience, filtering, and psychological distance are three key ideas connected to psychological and social boundaries (Antos, 2011). People's histories, perceptions, values, prejudices, needs, and expectations are among the areas of experience. Only within the boundaries of their respective specialties can senders encrypt and receivers decrypt messages. Communication becomes challenging when there is very little subject matter commonality between the sender and the recipient. By filtering, we mean that we typically only see and hear what is emotionally relevant to us. Our own needs and interests, which direct our listening, are the cause of filtering. Psychosocial barriers can involve an equivalent psychological to physical distance between people.

Effect of Communication on Employee Performance

According to mounting data linking workplace productivity to an organization's potential to influence the bottom line, communication is crucial (Muda et al., 2014). It has been suggested that those involved in communication

processes need to have both fundamental abilities and skills; otherwise, the information may not be understood correctly. In addition, it depends on the resources offered by organizations and the management's actions to determine whether the information is acceptable in order to have an accurate delivery (Chen, 2008). In obtaining such a good performance, the managers must show the initiatives of developing and providing opportunities to learn new skills to their employees through the communication process. Additionally, several research studies have looked into the relationship between employee performance and communication openness (Dwyer, 2005).

Empirical Review of the Study

As a result of this study, numerous academics and theorists have looked into it and produced numerous conclusions that are applied to the majority of current organizations in terms of effective communication. Results from a sample of 186 Assembly respondents showed a clear need for more regular communication and information exchange than is currently taking place. Similar research was conducted by Ainobushoborozi (2013) examined how worker productivity in civil engineering projects is impacted by good communication using a case study of Kampala Central division. The results revealed that timely information about changes impacting work and requests for clear communication and cooperation at work to complete tasks are statistically significant to labor productivity in civil engineering projects.

Conceptual Framework

This study adheres to the conceptual framework depicted in Figure 2 in light of the above analysis of related literature. The study has a strong emphasis on evaluating organisational communication and how it affects worker performance.

Independent variables

Figure2. The Conceptual Framework of the Study (Source: Own Literature Review)

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

According to Kothari (2004), it is essential to utilize an appropriate research design in order to choose the data collection tool, gather necessary and relevant data, and determine how data is organized and analyzed. The descriptive type of study design, according to Lee and Ling (2008), enables a researcher to gather information, summarize it, present the data, and analyze it for the goal of clarification. The main goals of descriptive research are to analyze correlations and fluctuations in the pertinent variables while describing specific ideas or opinions. Descriptive survey is the type of research design utilized in this study.

Research Approach

Admasu (2012) explains that combining qualitative and quantitative approaches can help overcome the flaws of each approach by utilizing its advantages. Any type of data deficiency can be handled by using mixed approaches. Therefore, a combination of qualitative and quantitative research methods was used in this study.

Data Sources and Collection Method

The study collected data from both primary and secondary sources. Empirical information for the primary data was gathered by administering standardized questionnaires. To promote legibility and increase response rates, the questions were kept brief and the wording as clear as possible. The Wachemo University faculty served as the primary source of data. To supplement the survey-based analysis, the secondary source of data was gathered from a variety of sources, primarily from relevant reports, websites, and literature. Both open-ended and closed-ended questions were included in the questionnaire; open-ended questions allow respondents to express their thoughts and feelings in their own terms.

Target Population

The entire number of cases of the type that are the focus of the study is referred to as the population. It can include things like persons, events, and even people (William, 2011). All Wachemo University staff members who work in one of the three vice president offices make up the study's population because it is the sum of the units the research seeks to examine. These include the offices of the academic vice president, the vice president for research and volunteerism, and the vice president for administration and development.

Sampling Technique and Sample Size

Because the total population could be too big to study, the researchers only allow respondents from a subset of the population that is representative of the entire population. The three vice president offices at Wachemo University were chosen by the researchers for this study. Wachemo University's employees were split into three strata, including those under the administrative and development vice-president office, the research and community service vice-president office, and the academic vice-president office. The sample was purposefully chosen for each office: from the academic vice-president office, the colleges of business and economics, social science, and agricultural science were chosen; from the research and community service vice-president office, the research directorate office, the community service directorate office, and the research publication office were

chosen. From the vice president for administrative and development's office: Finance office and Student service office was selected

Table 1. Sampling Technique and Sample Size

Office name	Sample under each office	Target population
Academic vice-president office	College of business and economics	66
	College of social science	80
	College of agricultural science	69
Research and community service vice-president office	Community service directorate office	4
	Research directorate office	4
	Institute of indigenous knowledge directorate office	4
	Research publication office	4
Administrative and development vice-president office	Finance office	15
	Student service office	15
Total		261

Operationalization of Variables

a) Dependent Variable

Employee performance is the dependent variable in this study, and the total impact of communication on employee performance is determined by utilizing a five-point Likert scale for questions with multiple items (1=strongly disagree and 5=strongly agree).

b) Independent Variables

Completion, accuracy, consideration, clarity, succinctness, courtesy, and concreteness will be used as independent variables in this study.

Table 2. Independent Variables

No	Variable	Definition	Measurement	Expected effect on Employees performance (+/-)
1	Completeness	It implies it must include all the relevant information as the intended audience requires.	Five point Liker scale strongly disagree to strongly agree	+
2	Correctness	Implies both the factual information including in communications and the language and grammar use are correct and well-timed.	Five point Liker scale strongly disagree to strongly agree	+
3	Consideration	The sender must take into consideration the receiver's opinions, knowledge, mindset, background, etc. In order to communicate, the sender must relate to the target recipient and be involved.	Five point Liker scale strongly disagree to strongly agree	+
4	Clarity	Implies the communication should be clear to sender then only the receiver will be sure about it. The message should emphasize on a single goal at a time and shall not cover several ideas in a single sentence.	Five point Liker scale strongly disagree to strongly agree	+
5	Conciseness	The message should be precise and to the point. The sender should avoid the lengthy sentences and try to convey the subject matter in the least possible words.	Five point Liker scale strongly disagree to strongly agree	+
6	Courtesy	Implies the sender of the message should be sincerely polite, judicious, reflective and enthusiastic.	(Five point Liker scale strongly disagree to strongly agree	+
7	Concreteness	Implies being particular and clear rather than fuzzy and general.	Five point Liker scale strongly disagree to strongly agree	+

Source : Own Literature Review

Methods of Data Analysis and Interpretation

To determine the impact of communication styles on employee performance, descriptive analysis and inferential analysis (Pearson Correlation and multiple regressions) were used in this study. The mean and standard deviation values are used to rank the variable in descriptive analysis. The primary inferential statistical techniques used in this study to examine the relationships between the dependent variable (employee performance) and the independent variables (completeness, correctness, consideration, clarity, conciseness, courtesy, and concreteness) were Pearson's correlation and multiple linear regressions.

An error term and a linear combination of the independent variables are used to define a dependent variable's value.

$$Y = \beta_0 + \beta_1X_1 + \beta_2X_2 + \dots + \beta_KX_K + E,$$

$$Y = \beta_0 + \beta_1X_1 + \beta_2X_2 + \beta_3X_3 + \beta_4X_4 + \beta_5X_5 + \beta_6X_6 + \beta_7X_7 + E$$

Where:

Y is the response or dependent variable- employee's performance

X1= Completeness

X2= Correctness

X3=Consideration

X4= Clarity

X5=Conciseness

X6= Courtesy

X7= Concreteness

β_0 is the intercept term. The intercept is defined as the average value of dependent variable(Y) when the effect of independent variables(X) is eliminated. $\beta_1, \beta_2, \beta_3, \beta_4, \beta_5, \beta_6,$ and β_7 are the coefficients associated with each independent variable which measures the change in the mean value of Y, per unit change in their respective independent variables. The regression coefficients are also interpreted as the, change in the expected value of Y associated with a one-unit increase in an independent variable with the other independent variables held constant.

E= is a vector of errors of prediction.

Model Test

A model test is used to determine whether a model is accurate and valid. When predictor variables—also known as independent variables—in a regression model have stronger correlations with one another than they do with the dependent variable, this is referred to as multicollinearity. Therefore, tests for heteroskedasticity and multicollinearity were performed when needed. The variance inflation factor (VIF) was used to test for multicollinearity. As a general rule, there is a major multicollinearity issue if a variable's VIF is more than 10. Regression analysis also makes the assumption that the mistakes share a common variance. We refer to errors as heteroskedastic if their variance is not constant. Running the `hettest` command in Stata enabled the Breusch-Pagan test of heteroskedasticity to identify this issue. The null hypothesis which states that the error term has constant variance (homoskedastic) will be accepted if the Chi-square calculated is less than the table value.

Validity Test

According to Creswell (2009), a test's validity refers to how well it actually achieves its intended purpose.

The questionnaires that were initially created using simple language phrases were validated by experts to determine the extent to which the items were appropriate in securing pertinent data for the study. This was done in order to ensure the validity of the instruments used to collect the data. Since determining the validity of the questionnaire exposes imprecise instructions and vague questions, the researcher conducted a pilot study to gain crucial feedback and suggestions from respondents regarding these issues. The issues raised by respondents were then refined and corrected. Finally, a sample of the respondents who participated will be given the updated surveys as soon as they are created. The aforementioned procedures improved the instrument's internal validity in the study as a result.

Reliability Test

Reliability analysis, according to Saunders et al. (2009), refers to the degree to which the method of data collection produces reliable findings, similar interpretations or conclusions would be drawn by other researchers, or there is transparency in how sense was made from the raw data. While reliability analysis uses Cronbach's Alpha to ascertain the connection between the items, dependability is a measure of internal stability and consistency.

One of the most often used reliability metrics, Cronbach's alpha assesses the internal consistency of a scale's items. It shows how closely related the questions on a questionnaire are to one another. The normal range of Cronbach's alpha value ranges between 0-1 and the higher values reflects a higher degree of internal consistency. According to David (2003), there are five levels of internal consistency reliability: Excellent (>0.9), Good (0.70.9), Acceptable (0.60.7), Poor (0.50.6), and Unacceptable (0.5).

According to a 5-point Likert scale in this study, which includes strongly agree, agree, uncertain (average), disagree, and strongly disagree, each statement was scored. An internal consistency reliability test was run on 261 Wachemo University staff members based on this. Based on the goals and research questions, instruments were created.

Ethical Consideration

According to Bryman and Bell (2003), plagiarism is the act of misrepresenting someone else's work as your own by taking credit for their hard work. It involves appropriating someone else's ideas and using them as your own. Because of this, care was taken to ensure that all work that was based on the ideas of other researchers was properly cited. According to Mugenda (2003), participation in research is completely voluntary and subjects are free to leave the study at any time without facing any repercussions. The researcher was required to disclose this to the respondents before starting the study. It was entirely voluntary; no respondent was forced to take part in the survey. As a result, for the purposes of this study, all participants were given adequate information regarding its objective, and replies to the questionnaires were thus based on informed consent. All of the sources consulted for this research project are duly recognized. Additionally, when gathering the data through the surveys, some ethical aspects will be adequately observed

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Data Analysis and Interpretation

Introduction

The research study intended to evaluate Wachemo University's organizational communication style and its impact on workers' performance. The study's findings are provided in this chapter by triangulating the findings from the various sources. There are two sections in the chapter. The study of the econometric findings from the questionnaire data is covered in the first section. The results and interpretation of the quantitative and qualitative data gathered by a questionnaire are covered in the second section..

Background Information of the Respondents

Gender of the Respondents

Table 3. Gender of the Respondents

Gender	Number	Percentage
Male	100	40
Female	150	60
Total	250	100

Source (Survey 2021)

Gender specification on the study is one of the need activities which must be included in demographic characteristics of the respondents. Therefore under the table1 below had shown 100 (40%) of the respondents were female and 150(60%) respondents were Male. This also indicated that there is gender inequality.

Age of the Respondents

Table 4. Age of the Respondents

Age	Number	Percentage
21-30	70	28
31-40	100	100
41-50	80	32
Total	250	100

Source (Survey 2021)

When we see the age composition of the respondents above in table 4, the majority of the sampled respondents' age group falls between the ages of 31 up to 40 which accounts 100 % of the total number of sampled respondents. The percentage of ages between 21-30, 21-30, 41-50 is 28% and 32% respectively. This shows the majority of respondents are between ages of 31 and 40 years in which they are active work. Also they are the age group expected to imitate and flexible according to the environment.

Job Level of the Respondents

Table 5. Job Level of the Respondents

Job Level	Number	Percentage
Management	35	14
Supervisory	75	30
Subordinate	140	56
Total	250	100

Source (Survey 2021)

With regard to the Job Level of the Respondents, the figure shows that majority of the respondents 140(56%) have subordinate level, 75(30%) respondents have supervisory level and the remaining 35(14%) have management level.

Table 6. Terms of Employment

Terms of Employment	Number	Percentage
Permanent	240	96
Contract	10	4
Total	250	100

Source (Survey 2021)

Table 6 shows that all the managers 240(96%), who participated in the study were employed on permanent terms. 10(4%) of the subordinates were also on contract terms.

Work Experience of the Respondents

Data on the work experience of the respondents was gathered, frequencies were computed and percentages calculated. The results were presented in The results were presented in Table 6.

Table 7. Work Experience

Work Experience	Frequency	Percentage
1-3 Years	85	34
4-6 Years	90	36
>6 Years	75	30
Total	250	100

Source (Survey 2021)

The analysis in Table 7 shows that 85(34 %) of the workers worked for 1-3 years .90 (36%) of them worked with the organization for 4-6 years and 75(30%) of the workers have worked for more than six years.

Communication Channels Used at WCU

The managers and subordinates were asked to mention the main channels of communication used in WCU. The frequencies were computed and percentages calculated. The results are presented in Table 7.

Table 8. Communication Channels Used in WCU

Communication channels	Frequency	Percentage
Letters and memoranda	80	32
Telephone/ e-mail	75	30
Posters and notice board	50	20
Face to face	40	16
Meetings	5	2
Total	250	100

Source (Survey 2021)

Data obtained in table 8 indicates that letters and memoranda are the used channels of communication at WCU. This was so because 80 (32%) of the respondents reported that they used letters and memoranda most of the time which was supported by 75 (30%) of the respondents who also indicated that they used telephone/ e-mail to communicate with them most of the time. The other mentioned channels of communication at WCU were the Posters and notice board, face-to-face oral communication, meetings.

Organizational Communication

Table 9. Organizational Communication

No	Item	Mean	Standard Deviation
1	Employees receive clear, accurate and prompt information on what the organization expects of them.	3.46	1.06
2	Employees are kept informed on matters that affect their work and the working conditions	3.05	1.195
3	Employees are given opportunity to voice their suggestions and fears.	3.10	1.090
4	The organization implements the views and opinions of workers.	2.28	1.223
5	The organization provides prompt feedback to the employees	4.0	1.0

Source (Survey 2021)

Respondents are asked about employees receive clear, accurate and prompt information on what the organization expects of them, the response shows that the mean of (3.46) and standard deviation of (1.06) shows that they have Employees receive clear, accurate and prompt information on what the organization expects of them. A mean of 2.7 and standard deviation of 1.28 clearly shows employees are kept informed on matters that affect their work and the working conditions. Similarly, respondents agree that employees are given opportunity to voice their suggestions and fears. The mean (2.28) and (1.22) shows the organization not implements the views and opinions of workers. The mean 4.00 and standard deviation of 1.0 indicates that the organization provides prompt feedback to the employees.

Organizational Communication

Table 10. Organizational Communication

No	Item	Mean	Standard Deviation
1	My superior provides Sufficient amounts of useful Information that I understand.	4.5	1.1
2	My superior share and respond to information in a Timely manner.	4.05	1.195
3	My superior actively listen to my viewpoints	4.10	1.090
4	My superior always speaks Politely and this motivates me to model him/her.	2.5	1.8
5	My superior maintains Essential information flows to me.	4.0	1.0

Source (Survey 2021)

The above table shows that mean of 4.5 and standard deviation of 1.1 indicates that superior provides sufficient amounts of useful information that employees understand. Similarly a mean of 4.05 and standard deviation of 1.19 clearly shows superior share and respond to information in a timely manner. The same is true for the question that superior actively listen to my viewpoints was agreed with the mean of 4.1 and standard deviation of 1.2. Mean of 2.5 and standard deviation of 1.0 clearly shows that Superior speaks less politely and this

demotivates workers. And they agree on the idea superior maintains essential information flows to workers.

Factor Analysis for Employee Performance

Table 11. Factor Analysis for Employee Performance

No	Item	Mean	Standard Deviation
1	I receive meaningful recognition for work well done.	4.4	1.06
2	I receive useful feedback from superior on my job performance	4.15	1.195
3	My work has made contribution to the good of the organization would please me	4.10	1.090
4	I like to feel that I am making some contribution not for myself but for the Organization as well.	3.88	1.223
5	I meet the formal performance I meet the Requirements of the job.	4.2	1.0

Source (Survey 2021)

The above table indicates that respondents receive meaningful recognition for work well done and they receive useful feedback from superior on their job performance. Similarly their work has made contribution to the good of the organization would please me and like to feel that they are making some contribution not for themselves but for the Organization as well. Also they meet the formal performance requirements of the job.

Results of Multiple Regression Analysis

Table 12. Result of Multiple Regression Analysis

Model	Unstandardized coefficient	Standardized coefficient	Std. error	p- value
Constant	-.260	-	.254	.307
Completeness	.023	.227	.007	.001
Correctness	.055	.041	.079	.048
Consideration	.190	.296	.038	.000
Clarity	.096	.283	.020	.000
Conciseness	.152	.202	.045	.001
Courtesy	.132	.186	.042	.002
Concreteness	.115	.159	.046	.015
F statistics	F(7,111)= 26.956			0.000
R ² (R ² adj.)	0.760(0.736)			

Source (Survey 2021)

As shown in table, the coefficients of the regression for Completeness (0.023, p < 0.01). This shows there is significant relationship between Completeness and employees performance of the organization. From this result we can understand that complete message helps to perform work well.

The other factor, Correctness is significant at 1 percent and 5 percent level of significance and it is concluded there is dependable pattern of relationship between Correctness of the message and employees performance.

Other factor Consideration (0.190, p < 0.01) is significant determinant to the performance of employees. When the Consideration level increases the performance of the employees also increases.

The regression output shows that Clarity of communication (0.096, p < 0.01), has a significant relationship with performance of employees. This

clearly shows that when the Clarity increases the performance will also increase. Hence the null hypothesis of the study which states that, there is significant relationship with performance of employees is accepted.

The result additionally exhibited that the other factor influencing employee's performance is Conciseness (0.132, $p < 0.01$), the regression result clearly shows that there is significant and positive relationship with the employees performance of organization. The result of regression helps to accept the null hypothesis which states that there is significant relationship on the employee's performance of in relation to the difference in Conciseness.

Other variable in this study is Courtesy (0.152, $p < 0.01$), as shown in the regression output it has positive and significant relationship with the employees performance. Also the hypothesis states that there is significant relationship on the employees performance and Courtesy of communication so this hypothesis is supported.

The other variable in this study which is expected to create variation on the employees performance of the organization is Concreteness (0.115, $p < 0.05$), shows there is significant relationship with employees performance of organization. Based on the regression result, the null hypothesis which states that there is significant relationship on the employee's performance of the organization in relation to the difference in Concreteness is accepted.

CONCLUSION

From the results, the communication systems frequently used include face-to-face, telephone, written memos, email/internet and grapevines, with the most useful channel of communication being face-to-face.

Communication in the organization serves for transmitting, for instance, commands and regulations, for reducing the ambiguous, and for creating and maintaining social relationships among the members in the organization which contributes to enhancing the employees' organizational commitment. In communication, employees get enough information to accomplish their tasks and receive feedback from managers to improve their performances; employees can give feedback to superiors about their tasks and give suggestions and critical opinions on how to improve organizational performance. All of these allow employees to know the organization better and it may cause them to form attachments with, identification to and involvement in the organization; good communication also provides an opportunity for employees to achieve their individual goals together with organizational goals; it also educates employees in the importance of obligation.

Furthermore, these results supported the relevant assumptions of human relations theory that emphasizes human needs and favors informal communication. It is important that the organization satisfies employees' needs for social interaction with management and especially provides opportunities for employees to achieve their self-actualization. Good communication is an essential condition for an organization to achieve the organizational goals, as well as individual goals. When the organization works well and cares about employees' individual development, the employees' highest level of need - that for self-actualization - can be fulfilled; thereby they can contribute best to the

organization. If the organization highlights each individual's capability and contribution, provides opportunities for them to participate in decision making, and encourages them to be more involved in the organizational operations, then the employees tend to commit at higher levels to the organization because they want to or ought to do so.

RECOMMENDATION

Employee performance can be further enhanced if bottlenecks in the communication systems are either removed or kept at their least. Particularly, information distortions caused by omissions and exaggerations must be addressed by both management and employees. There should be fewer distractions during communications in order to reduce or remove selective learning. Added to this, management must avoid communication overload because it reduces clarity in communication. Even though open and candid communication is encouraged, it is recommended that such communications come with courtesy and consideration, and without malice or prejudice.

The organization should reinforce a change in attitude among managers to promote effective communication. The respondents had suggestions as to the practices that could help eliminate ineffective communication. In particular, the organization should timely provision of feedback, respectful treatment of the workers, clear and comprehensive delivery of information, and accessible help and guidance on the part of the managers.

Timely delivery of information will also reduce time pressure on employees which more often than not reduce efficiency, effectiveness, productivity, and output. When information is delivered on time, it gives room for clarity to be sought to ensure concreteness and correctness.

The fact that face-to-face is considered a more useful channel of communication provides a unique opportunity for management to involve the grassroots in the formulation of policies as well as in decision-making. This will ensure employees feel valued and also elicit commitment to the implementation of decisions taking in order to achieve set goals and objectives.

Based on these findings, managers are recommended to make the following adjustments in their treatment of the workers, provide better guidance and help to the workers, be more available for assistance, offer help, and inquire if the workers are facing any difficulties; provide feedback on staff's performance regularly; avoid yelling at workers, getting annoyed, and using a disrespectful tone; and establish clear communication explain rules in a comprehensive manner, repeat and clarify if needed, perhaps create a leaflet and tips, provide employee handbooks, and use reminders.

To increase employee engagement and reduce turnover intention, managers are recommended to meet the employees half way and practice mutual understanding and support by means of establishing friendly and trustworthy relations. Managers are encouraged to identify employees' perceived barriers so that they can provide career assistance to employees by asking them directly in order to tackle the reasons that impede their career interests.

FURTHER STUDY

This research still has limitations, so it is necessary to carry out further research related to the topic of Assessing The Organizational Communication Style And Its Effect On Employees' Performance In The Case Of Wachemo University this research and add insight to readers.

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